

Electrokinetic Potential and Dielectric Constant: Quartz Systems

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The electrokinetic potential of the quartz system in mixed solvents has been studied. The results are found to be in agreement with the rule of Coehn and Raydt.

In a previous paper¹ the authors reported findings of their study on the dependence of electrokinetic potential with glass diaphragm on the dielectric constant of the medium by the electro-osmotic method. The work has been extended further in this communication to the case of quartz diaphragms.

As in the previous paper¹, the variation of dielectric constants of the media was brought about by addition of alcohol to water in different quantities. In practice, mixtures of methanol and water and ethanol and water in varying proportions were used as media. The range of alcohols studied extended from 0 to 90%. In most cases reproducible results could be obtained up to about 70% of alcohol. Beyond this, results with direct and reverse currents showed less satisfactory agreement with each other.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diaphragms were prepared from quartz, pulverised to 150 to 200 mesh. The sample of quartz, kindly supplied by the Central Glass and Ceramic Research Laboratory, was of good quality with little or no iron in it.

Lithium chloride solution (~ 5%) was used for the elimination of surface conductance. Details of the experimental methods used have already been described¹. Results obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Quartz diaphragm (150-200 mesh). Temp. = 35°. LiCl = 12.27 g. in 250 ml.

Alcohol (by vol.).	D.	η (poise).	η/D .	ζ -potential.	
				Obs.	Calc. from eq. (1).
		A. MeOH-H ₂ O mixtures.			
0%	76.00	0.00721	0.948×10^{-4}	41.15	..
10	74.30	0.00859	1.156	47.34	..
20	69.20	0.00956	1.381	41.69	42.92 mv
30	64.98	0.01078	1.683	40.20	40.77
40	60.74	0.01166	1.920	39.47	37.93
50	58.20	0.01158	1.993	35.35	36.23
60	55.85	0.01160	2.084	30.32	34.52
70	48.03	0.01015	2.114	24.83	29.44
80	42.10	0.00851	2.021	27.70	26.47

TABLE I (contd.)

Alcohol (by vol.).	D .	η (poise).	η/D .	ζ -potential.	
				Obs.	Calc. from eq. (1).
B. EtOH-H ₂ O mixtures.					
0%	76.00	0.00721	0.946×10^{-4}	41.15 mv	..
10	74.30	0.00955	1.285	55.95	..
20	68.40	0.01285	1.828	49.38	51.30 mv
30	60.78	0.01420	2.346	49.30	45.25
40	56.50	0.01568	2.651	47.44	41.82
50	50.58	0.01607	3.177	39.86	37.01
60	44.05	0.01642	3.072	34.10	32.45

DISCUSSION

The results show that due to addition of 10% alcohol to water, the ζ -potential of quartz diaphragm in contact with electrolyte solution increases slightly. With further increase of alcohol at constant lithium chloride concentration, the electrokinetic potential gradually decreases with decrease of dielectric constant of the medium.

The effect of dielectric constant on the electro-osmotic velocity of solid-liquid system was first studied by Coehn and Raydt². According to their rule, the negative ζ -potential of inert materials like glass, quartz, etc. ($D=4$ to 8) in various liquids will decrease with decrease of dielectric constant of the medium. Their empirical equation is

$$\frac{\zeta_x}{\zeta_a} = \frac{D_x - D_q}{D_a - D_q} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where D_x , D_q , and D_a refer respectively to dielectric constant of the unknown liquid, quartz, and of reference liquid and ζ_x and ζ_a , electrokinetic potential for the unknown liquid and for reference liquid respectively.

Fairbrother and Balkin³, Perrin⁴, and De Smet and Delfosse⁵, however, obtained results deviating widely from those of Coehn and Raydt².

In order to test equation (1) in the light of our results, the liquid mixture containing 10% alcohol was selected as the reference medium of dielectric constant D_a . The reason for this selection of medium will be evident from the fact that the ζ -potential, from this composition, gradually decreases with decrease of dielectric constant of the medium. As has already been mentioned, the decrease of negative ζ with decrease of dielectric constant is a primary requirement of equation (1). From the values of ζ_a and D_a for this reference medium, ζ_x for other liquid mixtures of dielectric constant D_x have been calculated and the results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 as smooth curves. The value of D_q ⁶ varies from 3.8 to 4.1 and a mean value 4.0 for the dielectric constant of quartz has been used in our calculation.

2. Coehn and Raydt, *Ann. Physik*, 1909, 30, 777, quoted by Abramson in "Electrokinetic Phenomena".

3. Fairbrother and Balkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 63, 389, 1564.

4. Perrin, *J. chim. phys.*, 1904, 2, 807; 1905, 3, 50.

5. De Smet and Delfosse, *Mémoires. Koninkl. Vlaam. Acad. Wetensch. Belg. Klasse Wetenschaf.*, 1942, 4, No 10.

6. Hodgman *et al.*, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., U.S.A.

It will be evident from the Fig. 1 that starting from the reference medium, the agreement between the observed electrokinetic potential with those calculated on the basis of equation (1) for different values of the dielectric constant is fairly good for MeOH—H₂O system. Here the observed ζ —%MeOH curve practically coincides with the theoretical curves obtained on the basis of eq. (1). In the case of EtOH—H₂O, the nature of the theoretical and experimental ζ —%EtOH curve is also very similar and the calculated values of ζ are not too far from the experimental values, as evident from Fig 2.

From this agreement, it may be concluded that Coehn and Raydt's rule is valid for electro-osmotic velocities of quartz diaphragm in contact with different compositions of water-alcohol mixtures containing the same amount of the electrolyte. The result with pure water, however, does not agree and contrary to Coehn's rule, addition of 10% alcohol to water, keeping the electrolyte concentration the same, increases the ζ -potential of quartz diaphragm, which it is very difficult to explain. Perhaps this initial increase in ζ -potential is due to the increased surface-charge effect on ζ -potential either by increase in adsorption of potential-determining ions or by primary change of solvation factors of the charged groups on the surface. It may also be due to the initial adjustment of the counter ions between the fixed and the diffuse part of the double layer. Further work is necessary to examine which of these effects is really operative for the electrokinetic behaviour of quartz diaphragm due to addition of 10% of alcohol in water.

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